

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327797165>

Assessment of Cement Handling Behaviour For Selected Construction Sites of Bhatbhateni Supermarket

Article · September 2018

CITATIONS

20

READS

1,325

2 authors:

[Anjay kumar Mishra](#)

Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal

310 PUBLICATIONS 985 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

[Er Umesh Chaudhary](#)

Nepal Engineering College Centre for Post Graduate, Nepal

2 PUBLICATIONS 39 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

<http://www.solidstatetechnology.us/index.php/JSST/issue/view/10> [View project](#)

Construction Management [View project](#)

Assessment of Cement Handling Behaviour For Selected Construction Sites of Bhatbhateni Supermarket

Anjay Kumar Mishra¹, Er. Umesh Chaudhary²

¹Ast. Professor at Shanker Dev Campus, T.U, Kathmandu, Nepal.

²Consulting Civil Engineer & Sr. Site Engineer.

Abstract

Cement is one of the most expensive and highly used construction materials. Overall objective of this study is to assess the cement handling behavior of brands available for ongoing construction projects of Bhatbhateni Supermarket at Bhaktapur, Butwal and Biratnagar. Sagarmatha, Shivam and Maruti brands of cements were found to be used in these projects for concreting works..

The average mean of compressive strength of concretes casted at field of Bhaktapur, Biratnagar and Butwal sites for M20 and M25 were 23.74 N/mm², 23.20 N/mm²& 24.50 N/mm² and 28.34 N/mm², 27.33 N/mm²& 29.29 N/mm² respectively which was found to be greater than the expected 28 days compressive strength at field conditions in both cases. Therefore, design mix made for M20 and M25 concretes at laboratory under study was found to achieve the strength required by concretes at all sites under case study. It was found that cement sacks have no manufacture date but the analysis of cement handling behavior at sites showed that cements were being consumed at sites within 1 month after arrival from the manufacturer. There was no wastage of cement due to satisfactory storing conditions at warehouse but, the curing methods of concrete were found to be upgraded by applying ponding and wet burlap techniques.

Inspection of cement in terms of quality should be done so that cement manufacturers could be compelled to maintain their quality.

Keywords: Ordinary Portland cement, Design Mix, Field Condition, Lab Condition, M20, M25

Background

Cement is a material having adhesive and cohesive properties enabling it to form good bond with other materials. In concrete, cement is the main constituent which is the only active binding media and the only component scientifically controlled. Cement has got the property of setting and hardening by virtue of chemical reactions with water at normal temperature.

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) is the most common type of cement in general use around the world because it is a

basic ingredient of concrete and mortar. It is a fine powder produced by grinding Portland cement clinker (more than 90%), a limited amount of calcium sulfate (which controls the set time) and up to 5% minor constituents (as allowed by various standards). The OPC or the Ordinary Portland Cement is the most widely produced cement in Nepal.

Also due to high consumption of cement, the production is also high which causes the increase in duration between manufacturing and use of the cement on construction work. The supply of cement from factory to supplier then supplier to consumer takes time and the manufactured

Corresponding Author: Anjay Kumar Mishra, Shanker Dev Campus, T.U, Kathmandu, Nepal.

E-mail Id: anjaymishra2000@gmail.com

Orcid Id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2803-4918>

How to cite this article: Mishra AK, Chaudhary U. Assessment of Cement Handling Behaviour For Selected Construction Sites of Bhatbhateni Supermarket. *J Adv Res Const Urban Arch* 2018; 3(3): 1-11.

Copyright (c) 2018 Journal of Advanced Research in Construction and Urban Architecture (ISSN: 2456-9925)

cement has to be stored in many places. The impact of age of cement and the impact due to storing are not taken much concern but it is very important factor for safe and sound construction work. Nepal lies in grade IV seismic zone and is very prone to the earthquake. For safe and sound structures not only the construction design but the use of construction materials should also conform to the standards to complete as a good engineering construction. Among the various commercial complexes that are being built, Bhatbhateni Supermarket is also one that is expanding its branches in different cities of Nepal due to its popularity in the supermarket and departmental store segment. Since, there are high numbers of occupants in these types of buildings, it is very necessary to keep the quality of construction in priority as well as the construction cost into consideration. . This study is focused on the assessment of cement handling behaviors being adopted at sites.

Research Objectives

The overall objective of the study was to assess the cement

A proper planning of construction materials can be done by applying Always Better Control (ABC) technique in which these materials can be grouped into high – value, medium – value and low – value materials. The cement is the most expensive construction material and easily deteriorates in terms of quality if delayed in consumption or if not taken proper care in transporting and storing situations. Thus, according to ABC analysis approach it can be classified in Group – A (Chitkara, 2013).

The cement management process is very crucial because if negligence is done then the project might face the problem of cost over – run. A proper cement management process includes acquisition of materials on sites, daily store operations, cement delivery by suppliers, cement inspection on site, protection of cement from damage during storage, and cement wastage control during utilization on site. Figure – 1 can be adopted as a technique for cement management process.

Figure – 1 shows a chain of material (e.g. cement) supply

(Modified from (Yusuf, Aji, Dammo, Arinze, Isa, & Deborah, 2015))

Figure 1. Material Chain Supply & Use Cycle

handling behavior at selected Bhatbhateni Supermarket sites with following specific objectives:-

- To evaluate the compressive strength of concretes casted at field whether meets the expected compressive strength or not; so that design mix could be ensured.
- To analyze the cement handling behaviors at sites under study; so that condition of cement could be known.

Literature Review

Cement Management Process

Materials management is the scientific method of procuring, storing, safeguarding, transporting and utilizing materials on site in order to ensure economy and achieve waste minimization (Yusuf, Aji, Dammo, Arinze, Isa, & Deborah, 2015).

and its use so that management of materials can be assured efficiently. In this system, Project Manager informs about the order size to the buying department. Buying department places the order to the supplier. The supplier dispatches the order with invoice papers to the site. After the arrival of goods at site, the store keeper checks the papers and damage of goods and then records it in “goods received book” as well as informs the store helper to store it safely in warehouse and forwards the invoices papers to store head. The store head monitors the deliveries and invoices and confirms the head office account section about the goods being received. After the conformation of items received, head office account section pays the supplier.

Simultaneously at site, the site engineer issues the order slip to the store keeper mentioning the amount of cement bags to be used in any activity. Then, the store keeper informs

the store helper to deliver the order from warehouse to supervisor who then consumes those cement bags at site. The store head monitors those issue slips issued by the site engineers and keeps updating about the stocks remained to the project manager. The project manager forecasts the volume of cement to be needed for his upcoming works and initiates the requisition of new order if required in right quantity at the right time.

Furthermore, the cement management process can be studied by knowing how the cement handling behavior is adopted at site which includes the entry of cement manufacture date, cement storing conditions, time taken to consume the cement after arrival at sites and wastage of cements at sites.

Cement Handling Behaviors

Manufacture Date of Cement: Day, Month and Year should be printed in each cement sacks by the manufacturer. As per Indian specification, the manufacture date should be mentioned in the cement as "For each calendar year the first week shall be counted as 7 days from 1st of January and subsequent weeks numbered serially accordingly. In such an event the bags shall be marked as W01.....W51, etc." (IS8112:1989, 2005).

It is advisable to use fresh cement as possible. Uses of old cement can lead various problems such as the development of cracks, leakages, corrosion etc. It also increases the maintenance cost of your structure and it affects the life of the structure. If cement bag is more than three months old, then cement should be tested for its strength before being taken into use. The reduction in strength with time is:

- a) 3months old – 20% reduction in strength
- b) 6 months old – 30% reduction in strength
- c) 12months old – 40% reduction in strength (Association of Engineers, 1981).

Storing Conditions of Cement: Following points should be followed to store cement in warehouse :-

- a) Should be stored in a dry and enclosed structure, protected from rains and moisture and the stacked cement bags should be kept covered with waterproof sheets or tarpaulin.
- b) The cement bags should be stacked off the floor on wooden planks in such a way, so that it is about 150 mm to 200 mm above the floor. The floor may comprise of lean cement concrete or two layers of dry bricks laid on well consolidated earth.
- c) A space of 600 mm all-round between the exterior walls and the stacks should be maintained, so that

adequate ventilation is provided to avoid the buildup of damp air.

- d) The height of stack should not be more than 10 bags to prevent the possibility of lumping under pressure
- e) Stack the cement bags in such a manner so as to facilitate their removal and use in the order in which they are received.
- f) Different types of cement must be stacked and stored separately (Padhi, 2014).

Curing of Concrete: Curing is the process of preventing the loss of moisture from the concrete while maintaining a satisfactory temperature regime. The intension of curing is to protect the concrete against :

- a) Premature drying out, particularly by solar radiation and wind.
- b) Leaching out by rain and flowing water.
- c) Rapid cooling during the first few days after placing
- d) High internal thermal gradients
- e) Low temperature or frost
- f) Vibration and impact which may disrupt the concrete and interface with bond to reinforcement.

Curing of concrete can be done by ponding water for horizontal surfaces, wrapping of wet burlap, plastic films or water proof papers in vertical surfaces (Marsh, 2003).

Quality Control of Concrete

Quality control of concrete works includes uniformity in sources of materials to be used in concretes like sand, aggregates, admixtures, water cement ratio, workability of concrete and uniformity in application of concrete constituents in the same proportion as stated in design mix. Quality control of concrete can be assured by the use of batching machines while mixing the ingredients of concrete.

Methodology

Study Area

This research is limited to the computation and comparison of the reinforced concrete quantity of the Bhatbhateni Supermarket that were constructed in Butwal, Bhaktapur and Biratnagar by the contractor Shine Builder's Engineering & Construction Pvt. Ltd. The research was focused to assess the cement handling behavior with the case of Bhatbhateni Supermarket. These three sites were selected on the basis of their locations (i.e. Western, Central & Eastern Regions of Nepal) so that if any variations in cement behavior due to location arise it may be included in the research.

Study Population

Table 1. Sample Size for Schedule Survey

S.No.	Particulars	Nos.
1	Contractor’s Site Engineer – 2 of each site	6
2	Contractor’s Site Store Keeper – 2 of each site	6
3	Contractor’s Supervisor - 1 of each site	3

Method of Data Collection

Compressive Strength

Cement mortar cubes (1:3) having an area 5000mm² were prepared (i.e. Nine cubes of each brand of cement) and tested in compression testing machine. The compressive strength at 3 days, 7 days and 28 days were found out.

Procedure:

- 200 grams of cement and 600 grams of standard sand (i.e. 200 grams of Grade – 1, Grade – 2 and Grade – 3) were mixed thoroughly.
- ((P/4)+3)% of water was added to the dry mix of cement and sand, (where P = % of water that was required for preparing paste of standard consistency). It was mixed thoroughly for a minimum of 3 minutes to obtain a mix of uniform color.
- The mould was filled with entire quantity of mortar using a suitable hopper attached to the top of the mould and was vibrated it for 2 minutes at a specified speed of 12000±400 per minute to achieve full compaction.
- The mould was removed from the machine and was kept in a place with temp of 27±2°C and relative humidity of 90% for 24 hours.
- At the end of 24 hours; the cubes were removed from the mould and submerged in fresh clean water. The

cubes were taken out of the water only at the time of testing (i.e. at 3, 7 & 28 days).

- The load was applied steadily and uniformly, starting from zero at a rate of 35 N/mm²/minute until the cube was not broken (IS:4031(Part-6)-1988, 2002).

Average Mean Compressive Strength of Concrete Cubes At Sites

Compressive strength reports were collected from all selected sites; i.e. Five test reports for M20 and M25 from all three sites. The average of 28 days compressive strength for all three sites was tabulated. The average mean of 28 days compressive strength tabulated in was calculated for each site.

Average Mean (a) = $\frac{\sum x}{n}$, where a = average mean of 28 days compressive strength, $\sum x$ = sum of all the values, n = numbers of values, and x = expected 28 days compressive strength at field.

If (a) ≥ x then, the strength would be achieved by concretes at field condition.

A Schedule survey with checklist was done with store keepers, site engineers and site supervisors involved in site for the construction to know about the cement handling behavior and quality of concreting being adopted at sites.

Table 2. Summary of Methodology

S.No.	Objective	Data Collected	Source of Information	Interpretation & Analysis
1	To evaluate the compressive strength of concretes casted at field whether meets the expected compressive strength or not; so that design mix could be ensured.	Compressive Strength test results of 7 days and 28 days were collected from each sites and the average mean was analyzed.	Compressive Strength test reports conducted at sites were analyzed to check the quality of concrete.	Qualitative analysis was done and the average means were evaluated.
2	To analyze the cement handling behaviors at sites under study; so that condition of cement can be known.	Manufacture date of cement, Storing conditions of cement at sites, Time period taken to use cement after arrival at site, slump tested results, etc. obtained at sites were noted.	Schedule survey was conducted.	Cement management practice being adopted at sites were analyzed and interpreted.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of the Concrete Strength between Lab and Field Conditions

The compressive strength of concretes were found to attain the expected compressive strength at 28 days i.e. 20N/mm² and 25N/mm² for M20 and M25 respectively.

Average means were calculated which showed that:-

- Bhaktapur site – At site conditions, the average mean of 28 days compressive strength was 23.74 N/mm² which was greater than the expected strength of 28 days for M20 concrete. Hence, the strength requirement by concrete at site was found to be achieved by the design mixed concrete.
- Biratnagar site – Similarly, the average mean of 28 days compressive strength was 23.20 N/mm² which was found to be greater than the expected strength of 28 days for M20 concrete (i.e.20 N/mm²). Hence, the strength requirement by concrete at site was found to be achieved by the design mixed concrete.
- Butwal site – Also, the average mean was 24.50 N/mm²

which was again found to be greater than expected strength of 20 N/mm². Hence, the strength requirement by concrete at site was found to be achieved by the design mixed concrete.

Similarly for M25

- Bhaktapur site – At site conditions, the average mean of 28 days compressive strength was 28.34 N/mm² which was greater than the expected strength of 28 days for M25 concrete. Hence, the strength requirement by concrete at site was found to be achieved by the design mixed concrete.
- Biratnagar site – Similarly, the average mean of 28 days compressive strength was 27.33 N/mm² which was found to be greater than the expected strength of 28 days for M25 concrete (i.e.25 N/mm²). Hence, the strength requirement by concrete at site was found to be achieved by the design mixed concrete.
- Butwal site – Also, the average mean was 29.29 N/mm² which was again found to be greater than expected strength of 25 N/mm². Hence, the strength requirement by concrete at site was found to be achieved by the design mixed concrete.

Cement Handling Behaviors

Manufacture Date

Plate 1.Cement used at site

In literature, it was reported that the manufacturer should print the manufacture date in cement sacks. Also, the consumers were promoted to use fresh cement and were advised not to use cements older than 2 months. But in field visit, the manufacture date in the Sagarmatha cement sacks was found to be missing whereas though the manufactured date was found in Maruti cement sacks, there was only information about the year and lot of manufacture. The information about day and month of manufacture was missing in Maruti sacks too. It was found that the contractor was using fresh cement that was directly delivered to the Bhatbhateni construction sites from the manufacturer.

Cement Storing Conditions

Plate 2. Cement Store at site

In all sites, the cement sacks were found to be stored in the shed made of C.G.I sheets with a damp proof floor. The floor of the store room was found to be raised from the existing ground level by laying one layer of dry bricks laid on well consolidated earth. Above, the layer of brick, wooden planks were found to be placed on which one layer of plywood were placed. The sheds were found to be covered by the tarpaulin sheets.

Plate 3. Cement Store at site

In all sites, the cement sacks were found to be placed by touching the exterior walls.

As per literature, a space of 600 mm all-round between the exterior walls and the stacks was to be maintained which was found not to be adopted at sites. Also, it was mentioned that different types of cement must be stacked and stored separately but in field, both P.P.C and O.P.C cements were found to be stored in a same warehouse. Hence, the cement sacks were found to be in satisfactory conditions free from moisture and direct contact with water and still the storing techniques needs to be upgraded at sites of Bhatbhateni Supermarket.

Time Period Taken to Consume Cement after Arrival at Site

The time period taken by the contractor to consume the cement bags was found to be within one month after arrival of cement bags at these three sites taken into consideration. The arrival date of cement sacks and the issued slips of cement consumption at sites were found. During the field visit, it was found that all three sites had no such bigger cement store to store more than 1200 sacks, so it showed that cements were being consumed within one month of arrival at sites. It was found that the Project Manager had already estimated the cement required in one month by the site and he was also found to be responsible for placing the order of cement at least 4 days prior to the demand at sites.

Slump Test

Plate 4. Slump Test performed at site

In plate no. .4, it can be seen that slump test had been performed to ensure the workability of fresh concrete during concreting activity at sites such as casting of slabs.

Plate 5. Slump Test performed at site

According to Plate No. .5, the slump value of the mixed designed concrete was found to lie between 110mm to 120mm. The slump tests were found to be performed at frequent intervals at site in order to ensure the consistency of the fresh concrete at site. Also, during the visit of sites the slump values of sites were found to satisfy the slump value limits provided by the design mix at lab.

Curing of Concrete

Plate 6. Curing of Concrete at site

The curing of concrete at sites was found to be done at least three times in a day. For curing of columns, it should be done by wrapping burlap all-round the columns which were missing at sites.

Plate 7. Curing of Concrete at site

For curing of slabs, it was again found that only water was sparked rather it must be done by adopting ponding technique. Hence, the curing activity at sites were found to be poor as the proper curing techniques like ponding of water for horizontal surfaces and wrapping of burlap for vertical surfaces were not adopted.

Quality Control of Concrete

From interview of project managers, it was found that the contractors were using the aggregates from the same sources that were used for design mix. There was no batching machine that could have assured the uniformity in relative proportions of ingredients in concrete. But, during field inspection it was found that relative proportions of ingredients were calculated in volume of standard cubic box used to measure sand and aggregates for concreting. Water in liters was found to set on mixture machine gauge by conducting slump test for workability. Also, compressive strength test was found to be conducted at sites to assure the achievement of strength requirement of concrete. The analysis of average mean of compressive strength discussed in first section showed that the strength requirements by concretes were achieved at sites. Hence, techniques applied for quality control was found to be satisfactory.

Key Findings

After collecting and analyzing primary and secondary data, the following information and results were found:

- The strength requirements by concretes at sites were found to be achieved by the design mixed concretes because the average mean of 28 days compressive strength of Bhaktapur, Biratnagar and Butwal sites for M20 & M25 concretes was 23.74 N/mm², 23.2 N/mm² & 24.50 N/mm² and 28.34 N/mm², 27.33 N/mm² & 29.29 N/mm² respectively which was greater than the expected compressive strength of 28 days for both concretes.
- Manufacture date was found to be missing in Sagarmatha cement bags whereas in Maruti cement bags there was only information about the year of manufacture and lot number.
- Warehouse of cement was found to be satisfactory and needed to be upgraded by adopting provisions of ventilation, providing a space of 600 mm all-round between the exterior walls and the stacks, and maintaining a separate warehouse for OPC and PPC cements.
- Consumption of cement was good as it was found to be consumed within 1 month after arrival at sites from manufacturer.
- Slump test was found to be conducted at sites on frequent intervals to ensure the workability of fresh concrete and the slump values were found to be maintained as provided by the design mix.

- Curing of concrete was found to be poor and the provisions like wrapping of burlap on columns and ponding of water for slabs were needed to be adopted.
- A cement management technique was found to be adopted by the contractor at sites under study during construction.
- Quality control of concrete was found to be satisfactory at all sites under study.

Conclusion

1. Design mix technique was found to be adopted by the contractor of Bhatbhateni Supermarket projects. It was also found that a cement management process of their own had been developed and adopted at sites when the cement handling behavior at their sites were analyzed. Only the lacking part was that the warehouse of cement needed to be upgraded and the curing technique was not proper.
2. Project managers were found to be aware about the design mix technique and the consequences of change in sources of sand, aggregates, and admixtures. But, the quality control technique for concrete was found to be satisfactory at sites since there was no batching plant for effective control in mixing of ingredients of concrete.

Recommendations

1. Trial mix design technique should be promoted so that the construction activity could become more economical without compromising the quality.
2. A proper cement management process needs to be developed and adopted in projects so that expensive material like cement can be obtained at right time at right place and consumed as fresh as possible.
3. Batching plants should be used in sites for achieving good control in quality of concrete while mixing relative ingredients of concrete.

References

1. Acharya PR. (2016). In: P Rimal (Edi) *The Himalayan Times; Business; Rendezvous*. Retrieved June 18, 2017, from The Himalayan Times: <https://thehimalayantimes.com/business/nepal-no-provision-certify-cement-higher-33-grade/>
2. Adeagbo D, Kunya S. Review of Waste Management Strategies on Nigerian Construction Sites. *ATBU Journal of Environmental Technology* 2003; 2: 49-50.
3. Aldieb MA, Ibrahim HG. Variation of Feed Chemical Composition and Its Effect on Clinker Formation - Simulation Process. *Proceedings of The World Congress on Engineering and Computer Science* 2010; 2.
4. Aligizaki K. Definition of Pore Structure parameters. In K. Aligizaki, *PoreStructure of Cement-Based Materials Testing, Interpretation and Requirements* 2006; (p. 19).

- Taylor and Francis Group.
5. Association of Engineers. Reduction of Strength of Cement. In *Civil Engineer's Hand Book*. Kerala: Kerala Public Works Department. 1981.
 6. ASTM: C114-07. In: AS Materials, Ed. *Standard Test Methods for Chemical Analysis of Hydraulic Cement* (Seventh Edition ed.) West Conshohocken, Pennsylvania, United States: American Section of the International Association for Testing Materials. 2007.
 7. Bohan R. (2017). *PCA - America's Cement Manufacturers*. Retrieved June 16, 2017, from www.cement.org: www.cement.org/cement-concrete-applications/how-cement-is-made
 8. Chitkara, K. (2013). Planning Construction Materials. In *Construction Project Management - Planning, Scheduling and Controlling* (Second ed., pp. 322,323). New Delhi, India: Tata McGraw Hill Education Private Limited.
 9. Duggal S. Materials for Making Concrete-I Cement. In S. Duggal, & S. Duggal (Ed.), *Building Materials* (Third Revised Edition ed., p. 146). New Age International 2009.
 10. Fathi DM. (2010). Introduction to Cement. In D. M. Fathi (Ed.), *Civil Engineering Materials SAB 2112* (p. 49). Malaysia: Department of Civil Engineering RAZAK School of Engineering & Advance Technology, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) International Campus.
 11. Gambhir, M. (2013). Concrete Making Materials-I: Cement. In P. Kundu (Ed.), *Concrete Technology: Theory and Practice* (Fifth Edition ed., pp. 6,22,30,31,32,33,34). New Dheli: Mc Graw Hill Education(India) Private Limited.
 12. Gambhir M. *CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY - Theory and Practice* (Fourth Edition ed., Vol. Fifth reprint 2010). (S. Shukla, Ed.) New Delhi, India: *Tata McGraw Hill Education Private Limited* 2010.
 13. Gambhir M. Properties of Fresh Concrete. In P. Kundu (Ed.), *Concrete Technology: Theory and Practice* (Fifth Edition ed., pp. 146,147,148,149,150). Delhi: TATA Mc Graw Hill Education(India) Private Limited 2013.
 14. Greenwood R. In *Construction Waste Minimization - Good Practice Guide*. Cardiff University, Centre for Research in the Built Environment 2003; 8-10
 15. Hanhan AA. *Influence of the SO3 Content of Cement on the Durability and Strength of Concrete Exposed to Sodium Sulfate Environment*. University of South Florida, Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering. University of South Florida. 2004.
 16. Harrisson. (2016, September 28). *CemNet.com the home of International Cement review*. Retrieved Dec. 07, 2017, from CemNet: <https://www.cemnet.com/Articles/story/160205/loss-on-ignition.html>.
 17. I.S:269:1989. (1993). *Ordinary Portland Cement, 33 - Grade Specification*. Bureau Of Indian Standards, Bureau Of Indian Standards. New Dheli: Bureau of Indian Standards.
 18. I.S:516-1959. *Methods of Tests For Strength Of Concrete*. Bureau of Indian Standards. New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards. 2002.
 19. Ibrahim S, Jamaa NB, Bagane M et al. The Effect of Raw Material's Fineness and Lime Saturation Factor on Clinker's Grindability and Energy Efficiency in the Gabes Cement Industry. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology (JMEST)* 2015; 2(11): 3149-3154.
 20. IS:4031(Part-5)-1988. *Determination of Initial and Final Setting Times*. Bureau of Indian Standards, Bureau of Indian Standards. New Delhi: *Bureau of Indian Standards* 2002.
 21. IS:4031(Part-6)-1988. *Determination of Compressive Strength of Hydraulic Cement other than Masonary Cement*. Bureau of Indian Standards. New Delhi: *Bureau of Indian Standards* 2002.
 22. IS:456-2000. *Plain and Reinforced Concrete - Code of Practice (4th Revision)*. Bureau of Indian Standards, Bureau of Indian Standards. New Delhi: *Bureau of Indian Standards* 2002.
 23. IS12269:1987. (1988). *Specification For 53 Grade Ordinary Portland Cement*. Bureau of Indian Standards, Bureau of Indian Standards. New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.
 24. IS8112:1989. *Scheme of Testing and Inspection For Certification of 43 Grade Ordinary Portland Cement IS8112:1989*. Bureau of Indian Standards, Bureau of Indian Standards. New Delhi: *Bureau of Indian Standards* 2005.
 25. Kiattikomol K, Jaturapitakkul C, Tangpagasit J. Effect of Insoluble Residue on Properties of Portland Cement. *Cement and Concrete Research* 2000; 30(8): 1209-1214.
 26. Laskar AI. Correlating slump, slump flow, vebe and flow tests to rheological parameters of high performance concrete. *Materials Research* 2009; 12(Jan./Mar. 2009), 6,7.
 27. Mahapatra AK. (2015, July 11). *Slide Share*. Retrieved Dec. 06, 2017, from Slide Share: <https://www.slideshare.net/arunkumarmahapatra1/effect-of-high-mg-o-on-cement-expansion>
 28. Marsh B. Curing. In J Newman, B Choo, *Advanced Concrete Technology*. Elsevier. 2003.
 29. Mishra AK, Regmi U. Effects of Price Fluctuation on the Financial Capacity of "Class A" Contractors. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts* 2017; 5(4): 1920 - 1937.
 30. NBC101:1994. *NS 49/2041 Ordinary Portland Cement*. Department of Building, UrbanDevelopment and Building Construction. Kathmandu: Government of Nepal Physical Planning and Works. 2064.
 31. Neville A. Selection of Concrete Mix Proportions (Mix Design). In *Properties of Concrete* (Fifth Edition ed., p. 2356). England, England/London: Pearson Education Limited 2011.
 32. Padhi S. (2014, Nov. 13). *CIVILBLOG.ORG*. Retrieved

- 12 12, 2017, from <http://civilblog.org/2014/11/13/how-to-store-cement-on-site/>
33. Raj N, Ilakkiya D. (2014). *masterbuilder.co.in*. Retrieved 06 18, 2017, from <https://www.masterbuilder.co.in/mix-design-m40-grade-concrete-per-102622009/>
34. Singh V, Marripoodi K. (2016). *Happho*. Retrieved December 03, 2017, from Happho: <http://www.happho.com/choose-building-materials-estimate-cost-quantities-house-construction/>.
35. Sinha S. (2002). *Reinforced Concrete Design* (Second Revised Edition ed., Vol. Eighth reprint 2007). New Delhi, India: Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
36. Srinivas, K. (2016). *Quora.com*. Retrieved 06 21, 2017, from <https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-workability-of-concrete>
37. Suvasan C. (2013, Sep.). *Indian Cement Review*. Retrieved Dec 2017, from Indian Cement Review: <http://www.indiacementreview.com/News.aspx?nId=1P2FASAdxyKwVwAoCBYPEg==>
38. Swenson E, Evans H. (1953). *Determination of The Specific Surface Area of Cements and Pozzolans by The Blaine Air Permeability Method*. National Research Council Canada, Division of Building Research. Ottawa: National Research Council Canada.
39. Thomas J, Jennings H. (2017). *The Science of Concrete*. Retrieved Dec. 13, 2017, from www.iti.northwestern.edu: http://iti.northwestern.edu/cement/monograph/Monograph3_7.html
40. Tripathi A. (2015, July). *New Business Age*. (New Business Age) Retrieved December 03, 2017, from New Business Age: <http://www.newbusinessage.com/MagazineArticles/view/1250>
41. Winter N. (2005). *Understanding Cement - Interpreting Cement Science Since 2005*. (WHD Microanalysis Consultants Ltd.) Retrieved December 04, 2017, from Understanding Cement - Interpreting Cement Science Since 2005: <https://www.understanding-cement.com/parameters.html#>
42. Yusuf G, Aji A, Dammo A, et al. Challenges Regarding Management Practice Of Cement On Construction Sites North-Eastern Nigeria. (I. 2278-7461, Ed.) *International Journal of Engineering Inventions* 2015; 4(8): 23-26.

Date of Submission: 2018-07-27

Date of Acceptance: 2018-08-28